
**FUNCTIONAL ALL-AROUND (CROSSFIT) AS AN INNOVATIVE SYSTEM
OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF CADETS OF THE MINISTRY OF INTERNAL
AFFAIRS OF THE ACADEMY OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

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Annotation.

One of the priority tasks of physical education in the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the preservation and strengthening of students' health, the formation of their values of a healthy lifestyle, motivation for physical education. Today, innovative technologies of physical education, fitness and health saving are relevant, as well as ways of generating physical fitness, focused on the personality-centered, comprehensive nature of education. Such technologies include functional all-around - crossfit, as technologies with ideological attitudes to a healthy lifestyle, an attractive competitive program and a variety of exercises for body correction.

Keywords.

functional all-around, crossfit, innovation, physical education, cadet, physical culture, sport.

Innovation is an implemented innovation that provides a qualitative increase in the efficiency of processes or products that are in demand by the market. It is the end result of a person's intellectual activity, his imagination, creative process, discoveries, inventions and rationalization.

From this definition, we see that crossfit corresponds to the signs of innovation:

As a system of physical training and at the same time a competitive sport, it appeared in 2001 in California under the authorship of Greg Glassman. The main

distinguishing feature of crossfit from other sports is the lack of specialization in it, the task of crossfit is more global – the athlete must simultaneously develop all physical qualities as much as possible [1]. This is attractive both for athletes and athletes – some get the most harmonious physical development, others test their abilities on all fronts, and, finally, both receive an unprecedented variety of training. In addition, the inconsistency and unusual nature of this system gave rise to a new wave of creative activity among coaches around the world: they faced a task that they had not previously encountered – to prepare an athlete for everything at the same time. Thus, we can say with confidence that crossfit, or functional all-around, is currently an innovation in the world of sports and physical education.

Platon said: "The proportionality of beauty and health requires not only education in the field of science and art, but also a lifetime of physical exercise."

The key words in this phrase are the words "all my life" - this is the secret of building a harmonious personality. With the growth and improvement of technology, modern people have received the widest opportunities for education from almost anywhere in the world and, at the same time, the opportunity to almost not move: we sit at work, at home, while studying and on the way anywhere, thereby depriving ourselves of the necessary physical activity. Meanwhile, human health is almost directly dependent on the level of his physical activity and with age this dependence only strengthens. Optimal physical activity contributes to maintaining normal weight and body composition, ensures proper muscle tone and normal bone mineralization, reduces age-related loss of their density, and also supports and improves the functioning of internal organs and the nervous system [2]. Physical education lessons at the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Academy of the Republic of Uzbekistan should give cadets and students what they need, and everyone's needs are different: one is health, others would like to correct posture or add aesthetic appeal to the body, others use physical culture to relieve nervous tension, to educate character. In addition, interests differ by gender and age: younger children are interested in playing, showing physical qualities such as speed, dexterity, strength, and at an older age, thoughts about the priority of health may already appear; on average, boys are more interested in developing strength, endurance, and speed than girls, and girls are more interested in flexibility, grace, and aesthetic side than boys. Some guys have been thinking since childhood or adolescence about what physical qualities will be useful to them in their professional activities and try to develop them, while others go because they

feel interest, positive emotions during classes and additional communication, belonging to a group. Currently, fitness has become quite affordable, but still not every student has funds for a subscription to a club with sufficient equipment and a modern material and technical base. In addition, ordinary fitness clubs assume either that their clients have certain knowledge and skills, or that they have funds for a personal trainer. At the same time, clubs offering crossfit training appear everywhere, during which full halls of athletes of different genders and ages gather and work according to certain programs under the guidance of coaches. This type of fitness seems to be the best option for extracurricular activities of cadets. The word crossfit is of English origin and is formed by the combination of two words: cross - combine, cross, force, and fit - strong, healthy, in good physical shape[2]. Crossfit in a broad sense is a training system designed to develop all muscle groups and all physical qualities of the student: speed, strength, endurance, flexibility, agility, coordination, etc. Crossfit trainings and competitions test an athlete not only with extreme loads, but also with unpredictability - this is one of the main features of crossfit: preparation for everything. Perhaps all this together has led to a rapid increase in the popularity of this type of fitness all over the world. In our country, there is an analogue of crossfit - functional all-around, essentially repeating its main features: the development and testing of all physical qualities within the framework of competitions, the resulting variety of training loads, the relative unpredictability of competitive activity. Crossfit has partly become popular due to the fact that by varying the load it can be included in the training plan for any sport, as well as used for people with a variety of characteristics and level of training. For cadets, it is also the development of moral, volitional and personal qualities through overcoming difficulties, self-discipline and physical work despite mental fatigue, prevention of inactivity arising from high classroom and extracurricular workload.

Crossfit workouts include exercises from different sports: weightlifting, athletics, gymnastics, powerlifting, kettlebell lifting, swimming, rowing and even skiing.

The use of crossfit in physical education classes in higher education institutions contributes to the comprehensive development of physical and mental qualities due to a high-intensity training program aimed at training all muscle groups, including the heart, the development of the respiratory system and increasing overall endurance, as well as due to the need to overcome fatigue, muscle pain, the desire to give in and give up [3]. At the same time, the group

format of training provides moral support during the execution of the complex: no one wants to be weaker than a friend or slower – it stimulates self-improvement and makes you look for strong-willed and physical reserves within yourself.

Crossfit-is:

1. Simple – even the simplest equipment can be used for a full workout: a horizontal bar with bars and a stadium, or a barbell and a pair of dumbbells or weights. If desired, you can train without any equipment at all, using only your own body weight.

2. Universally – by varying the load, the set of exercises, the training method, you can achieve various individual goals: reducing the fat component of the body, increasing muscle mass, developing mainly strength, endurance, speed or power while maintaining other physical qualities at a certain level.

3. Interesting – thanks to the wide variety of exercises and load modes, such workouts do not have time to get bored. In addition, the competitive element creates additional interest in the lesson. Against the background of a large number of absenteeism by cadets of physical education classes, this becomes a very important and relevant plus. At each lesson, cadets will be waiting for something new: training with or without weights, working with a hammer, martial arts exercises, gymnastic elements - everyone will like something of their own. Perhaps crossfit will become an incentive for some cadets to engage in one of the sports in more depth, having discovered some predispositions.

4. Effective – in essence, crossfit is a system of general physical training that stimulates the body to adapt to training stimuli of various kinds, without specialization on any one. Due to this, students can get a harmonious and uniform physical development.

5. Health improvement – crossfit is not only an extreme load, training can and should be built taking into account the training of those involved, gradually moving from moderate intensity to a higher one, in order to foster in them a stable habit of a healthy lifestyle and regular physical training.

Crossfit (functional all-around) is a training system and a sport in which athletes try to achieve the maximum development of all physical qualities at the same time and show them in non-standard conditions (crossfit competitions assume that athletes learn the task immediately before the start). Both training and crossfit competitions include performing exercises from different sports: gymnastics, weightlifting, athletics, swimming, etc. - in different sequences and with different modes of operation. For example, a competitive task may require an

athlete to first show maximum strength in three deadlift attempts, and then strength endurance and speed in performing the maximum number of medball throws, and all this in a limited period of time.

Thus, the crossfit training system is different:

1. Constant changes in the regime of loads and exercises performed;
2. High intensity of complex execution;
3. Linking exercises in long and short series;
4. The minimum possible rest time between sets, repetitions and series;
5. Lack of age and gender restrictions for classes;
6. Scalability for the physical capabilities and individual characteristics of each athlete [3].

The socio-cultural situation at the present stage of education development is characterized by the introduction of many innovations in the field of education and upbringing. At the same time, new ways of solving the health-saving problems of cadets and the younger generation as a whole are reflected. The future of the country, its gene pool, scientific, economic development of the state and other demographic indicators are directly dependent on the health of children and adolescents, and this makes it a subject of primary importance and timeless relevance regardless of any circumstances.

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